

Assessing Environmental Suitability for Mediterranean Marine Aquaculture Using Fuzzy Logic and Einstein Operators

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Abstract

Marine aquaculture in the Mediterranean Sea faces increasing environmental variability due to climate-driven changes in oceanographic conditions. Identifying suitable farming areas that ensure ecological sustainability and production stability therefore requires modelling tools capable of integrating multiple stressors and their non-linear interactions. This study proposes an environmental suitability index for *Sparus aurata* based on fuzzy set theory combined with Einstein sum and product operators. Species-specific tolerance ranges were used to construct fuzzy membership functions for key environmental variables such as sea surface temperature, current velocity, and wave height. These were aggregated into a multivariate suitability index (MSI) using Einstein operators, which allow for flexible, non-linear integration of interacting stressors. The approach was empirically evaluated along the southeastern Spanish Mediterranean coast using observed mortality data to assess its ecological realism. Results indicate that the Einstein-based MSI better captures the gradual transitions between suitable and unsuitable conditions than linear or fixed-weight methods, thus providing a more transparent and biologically meaningful assessment of site suitability. The framework offers a reproducible tool for marine spatial planning and the designation of Allocated Zones for Aquaculture (AZAs), supporting the development of climate-resilient aquaculture under changing environmental conditions.

Keywords: fuzzy logic; Einstein operators; environmental suitability; marine spatial planning; *Sparus aurata*; Mediterranean aquaculture.

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1. Introduction

Marine aquaculture is an increasingly important contributor to global food security and regional economies, particularly within the Mediterranean basin [1]. Yet, the sector faces growing vulnerability to climate-driven shifts in oceanographic conditions, including rising sea surface temperatures (SST) associated with marine heatwaves, enhanced stratification, and the consequent alteration of other oceanographic variables. These changes complicate the identification of Allocated Zones for Aquaculture (AZAs) and the selection of suitable farming sites in both coastal and offshore environments. The designation of

AZAs requires tools that are not only ecologically robust but also operationally transparent, enabling regulators and producers to balance environmental, social, and economic constraints [2,3].

Climate change poses a major challenge when evaluating AZAs, since in some cases an expansion of aquaculture may enhance production and growth of cultured species [4], while in others it increases stress levels to the point where the effects become detrimental [5]. Recent studies, such as Haberle et al. [6], attempt to assign viability values for aquaculture across the Mediterranean. This concern is particularly acute because the Mediterranean Sea is among the most affected regions by rising temperatures, as it is a semi-enclosed basin with limited circulation. Rising sea surface temperature (SST), altered current regimes, oxygen depletion, and ocean acidification are among the key stressors affecting both the physiology of cultured species and the reliability of long-term site planning [7–9]. *Sparus aurata* (gilthead seabream), as other main aquaculture species, exhibits thermal optima that, when exceeded, can lead to immunosuppression, metabolic disruption, and increased mortality [10–13].

In addition to thermal stress, hydrodynamic forcing represents a critical determinant of farm performance. Elevated current velocities can increase the metabolic cost of swimming, reduce feeding efficiency, and, in extreme cases, induce mechanical stress on both fish and cage structures [14,15]. Similarly, high wave heights and storm-driven sea states have been linked to infrastructure failures and behavioral alterations in farmed fish, which may reduce growth rates and elevate mortality risk [16–18]. Prolonged exposure to combined wave–current forcing can further constrain the effective habitat space within cages, potentially amplifying density-dependent stressors such as disease transmission [19–21].

In the worst-case scenario, persistent hydrodynamic stressors may cause partial or total net rupture, leading to the escape of farmed fish. Such escapes not only have negative repercussions for the aquaculture industry but also profound ecological impacts. The sudden release of large numbers of non-native predators can disrupt trophic dynamics and destabilize the ecosystem. In addition, the genetic variability of wild populations may be altered through interbreeding, while parasites and pathogens from farms can disperse across the surrounding habitat [22].

Given the growing evidence that hydrodynamic stressors such as waves and currents can amplify density-dependent risks and interact with other environmental drivers, there is a pressing need for suitability modelling tools that can explicitly quantify how ‘favorable’ or ‘unfavorable’ specific sites are for aquaculture. Such tools are essential to guide the designation of AZAs and to support evidence-based spatial planning under variable and changing environmental conditions.

Environmental suitability modelling has become a central component of marine spatial planning, with early efforts often adapting the terrestrial Habitat Suitability Index (HSI) framework to marine environments. One notable example is the work of Brown et al. [23], who proposed HSI models for fish and invertebrate species in coastal Maine based on expert-defined suitability indices (SI) for individual environmental variables. Although straightforward and operationally useful, these early models suffer from important limitations: they impose abrupt SI values that fail to capture gradual ecological responses. As a result, they may overlook complex synergistic or antagonistic effects among stressors that are ecologically relevant but masked by rigid index structures.

Beyond the early HSI-based approaches, more sophisticated methodologies have been developed to support aquaculture site selection, particularly through spatial multi-criteria evaluation frameworks coupled with GIS. For example, Dapuetto et al. [24] applied a multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) to identify offshore aquaculture sites in the Ligurian Sea

(Italy), integrating environmental, socio-economic, and regulatory criteria. More recently, Petrosillo et al. [25] proposed a framework for sustainable marine spatial planning of aquaculture that similarly relied on assigning fixed scores to a suite of environmental and socio-economic indicators, which were then aggregated into a multivariate suitability index using weighted linear combinations. These frameworks represented a methodological advance by explicitly accounting for spatial heterogeneity and by allowing the inclusion of multiple constraints, thus providing decision-makers with practical maps of site suitability. However, they remain largely dependent on expert-defined rules, rigid SI values, and linear weighting schemes, which limit their ability to capture gradual physiological responses or non-linear interactions among stressors.

Fuzzy set theory [26] appears to overcome this limitation by providing a formal framework to represent gradual transitions instead of rigid SI values. A fuzzy set is defined by a membership function that assigns each element a degree of belonging in the interval [0,1], thus allowing concepts such as 'suitable' or 'unsuitable' to be expressed in continuous rather than binary terms [27]. This framework allows optimal and lethal tolerance ranges, together with expert knowledge, to be incorporated in a transparent and interpretable way.

On the other hand, fuzzy arithmetic introduces algebraic operations—such as addition, multiplication, or specialised operators like Einstein sum and product—that allow fuzzy sets to be aggregated [27]. Through these operations, information from several fuzzy sets can be combined into a single representation. In practice, this means that the SIs derived for individual environmental variables can be integrated into a multivariate suitability index (MSI) that reflects the joint effect of multiple stressors. While a univariate fuzzy set captures the suitability of a single variable in isolation, fuzzy arithmetic enables the construction of multivariate indices that account for interactions among variables, thereby providing a more comprehensive measure of overall environmental suitability.

To sum up, fuzzy membership functions and algebraic operators offer greater flexibility and ecological realism in aggregating environmental information into multi-criteria evaluation frameworks. Since their adoption, fuzzy membership models have been applied in environmental assessments, including estimating greenhouse gas emissions [28], assessing habitat suitability [29], assessing the vulnerability of marine species to climate change [30], and investigating fishery production [31]. Although widely applied in environmental modelling, these approaches present certain limitations, as they rely heavily on expert-defined thresholds and membership functions, which may introduce subjectivity and reduce reproducibility. Nevertheless, they remain a valuable alternative when qualitative expert knowledge is central to the assessment [27]. Given these methodological considerations, special attention must be paid to how individual SIs are aggregated into MSIs, since the choice of aggregation operator determines how compensatory or limiting effects among stressors are represented.

MSIs are widely used to condense complex multidimensional information into a single, interpretable metric [32–34]. Their design must carefully consider both the context of application and methodological transparency to ensure robustness and minimise subjectivity throughout the construction process [35]. This study aims to develop and evaluate an MSI that effectively captures environmental conditions relevant to aquaculture sustainability along the southeastern Spanish Mediterranean coast. The proposed framework is centred on a non-linear aggregation strategy based on Einstein sum and product operators, integrated with: (i) species-specific fuzzy membership functions reflecting tolerance thresholds; (ii) non-linear aggregation through Einstein sum and product operators to account for potential interactions among environmental stressors; (iii) lagged effects of environmental variables; and (iv) empirical validation using observed mortality data for *Sparus aurata*. The

overarching goal is to identify the MSI formulation that best explains observed mortality patterns, thus serving as a reliable proxy for site suitability.

While the Einstein-based approach is the core focus of this work, we also tested two widely used multivariate techniques for MSI construction—Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR). These methods are among the most commonly applied tools for constructing multivariate suitability indices [32–34]. Their inclusion in our analysis serves both to benchmark the performance of the Einstein-based indices against established methodologies and to strengthen the robustness of our conclusions.

In addition, spatial trend analysis based on the Mann–Kendall statistic is employed to assess the temporal evolution of habitat suitability under historical climatic conditions [36,37].

The framework is applied to a defined marine region with the aim of addressing the following research questions:

1. Which MSI structure most accurately captures mortality risk and, by extension, site suitability for aquaculture?
2. Which environmental variables and time lags are most influential in driving mortality?
3. Based on the best-performing MSI, which zones within the study area offer the highest long-term potential for sustainable aquaculture operations?

2. Materials and Methods

We analysed a suite of physical and biogeochemical variables within a defined region of the western Mediterranean Sea, focusing on the southeastern Spanish coastline (Figure ??). Several reprocessed and reanalysis datasets from the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) were used. These products provide consistent, long-term, and high-resolution information based on satellite observations, numerical models, and data assimilation. Their spatial resolution ranges from 0.05° to $1/24^\circ$ ($\sim 4\text{--}5$ km), and they span periods from the early 1980s or 1990s up to approximately one month before present.

Sea surface temperature (SST) data were obtained from the SST_MED_SST_L4_REP_OBSERVATION product [38], which provides daily, optimally interpolated L4 SST at 0.05° resolution derived from ESA Climate Change Initiative records. Salinity (SO) and the eastward (u_o) and northward (v_o) ocean current components—used to compute the velocity modulus ($VM = \sqrt{u_o^2 + v_o^2}$)—were retrieved from the MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_006_004_E3R1 reanalysis [39]. This product provides hydrodynamic model outputs (NEMO + OceanVAR) at $1/24^\circ$ resolution with 141 vertical levels, assimilating sea level anomalies and in situ profiles. Chlorophyll-*a* concentration (CHL), dissolved oxygen (O_2), dissolved inorganic carbon (CO_2), and pH fields were obtained from the MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_BGC_006_008 biogeochemical reanalysis [40]. This dataset is produced with the MedBFM3 model at $1/24^\circ$ resolution (1999–present), assimilating surface chlorophyll from ESA-CCI. Finally, significant wave height (WH) was sourced from the MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_WAV_006_012 dataset [41]. This dataset consists of hourly wave parameters from WAM 4.6.2 at $1/24^\circ$ resolution (1985–present), assimilating altimeter wave height and forced with ERA5 winds.

All variables were interpolated and regridded to a common spatial resolution of $0.042^\circ \times 0.042^\circ$, using the med-cmcc-sal-rean-d grid as a reference, and subsequently merged into a unified database through the copernicusmarine Python (v3.9) library.

2.1. Mortality Dataset

The mortality dataset analysed in this study was provided by the General Directorate of Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries of the Generalitat Valenciana. It comprises 974 records collected between January 2015 and June 2022 across 35 aquaculture faci-

ties in the Valencian Community, with reported mortality percentages ranging from 0 to 53%. Although the dataset covers several cultured species—including European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*), Mediterranean mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*), meagre (*Argyrosomus regius*), and greater amberjack (*Seriola dumerili*)—we focused exclusively on gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*), the most represented species with 262 records. Restricting the analysis to seabream ensured homogeneity and alignment with the species for which environmental tolerance thresholds are well defined, thus providing a robust empirical basis for linking environmental suitability indices to farm-level mortality outcomes.

To ensure consistency between environmental drivers and observed biological responses, environmental variables were extracted for the same dates and at the grid cells closest to the farm locations where *Sparus aurata* mortality was recorded, with all observations falling between 18 February 2015 and 7 March 2022. For continuous spatio-temporal analyses, the complete interpolated dataset was considered within the domain $[-0.58^\circ, 1.46^\circ]$ longitude, $[38.06^\circ, 40.94^\circ]$ latitude, and from 1 January 2000 to 31 May 2023.

2.2. Fuzzy membership functions

Environmental suitability for each variable x was quantified using *fuzzy membership functions* (FMFs), which transform raw environmental values into continuous suitability scores $C(x) \in [0, 1]$. This approach, rooted in fuzzy set theory [?], represents the degree to which an environmental condition is favourable rather than imposing binary thresholds. From a statistical standpoint, FMFs ensure continuity and differentiability of the suitability surface, while from an ecological perspective they capture the gradual physiological responses that are typical of aquatic organisms.

For each environmental driver x_j , the single suitability index (SSI) is defined as:

$$SSI_j = \mu_j(x_j) = f_j(x_j; \theta_j), \quad (1)$$

where $f_j(\cdot)$ is the selected membership function and $\theta_j = (th_{inf}^{mort}, th_{inf}^{opt}, th_{sup}^{opt}, th_{sup}^{mort})$ denotes the vector of species-specific thresholds.

Among the several FMFs available in the literature (e.g., triangular, Gaussian, logistic, sigmoidal), we adopted the *trapezoidal* function (Eq. 2) because it distinguishes lethal and optimal ranges while maintaining a simple, interpretable, and computationally stable form suitable for integration with fuzzy algebraic operators. Whenever empirical evidence suggested asymmetric or gradual responses, alternative forms (e.g., logistic or sigmoidal) were tested for sensitivity. These tests confirmed that the trapezoidal shape offered the best compromise between ecological realism and mathematical robustness.

$$C_{trap}(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x \leq th_{inf}^{mort} \text{ or } x \geq th_{sup}^{mort}, \\ \frac{x - th_{inf}^{mort}}{th_{inf}^{opt} - th_{inf}^{mort}}, & th_{inf}^{mort} < x < th_{inf}^{opt}, \\ 1, & th_{inf}^{opt} \leq x \leq th_{sup}^{opt}, \\ \frac{th_{sup}^{mort} - x}{th_{sup}^{mort} - th_{sup}^{opt}}, & th_{sup}^{opt} < x < th_{sup}^{mort}. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In this formulation, each th term represents a *threshold* value defining the lower (*inf*) and upper (*sup*) bounds of either lethal (*mort*) or optimal (*opt*) conditions for the species. Specifically, th_{inf}^{mort} and th_{sup}^{mort} indicate the environmental limits beyond which survival is not possible, while th_{inf}^{opt} and th_{sup}^{opt} delimit the range within which physiological performance is maximal. Values between lethal and optimal thresholds correspond to suboptimal but tolerable conditions, where suitability decreases linearly as environmental stress increases.

The parameters of the trapezoidal function were defined using species-specific tolerance limits derived from the literature and empirical observations (Table 1). For environmental variables lacking experimental data, the 0.05 and 0.95 percentiles of the distributions observed at *Sparus aurata* farming sites were used to estimate ecologically realistic tolerance ranges, thereby avoiding extreme outliers while ensuring biological relevance.

Table 1. Threshold values used for each environmental variable in the fuzzy suitability model for *Sparus aurata*. Notes: ^a Upper mortality threshold for velocity modulus from Alfonso et al. [42]. ^b Optimal thresholds for CO₂ and velocity modulus defined as the 0.05 and 0.95 percentiles of environmental distributions observed at farming sites. Remaining values from Fourdain et al. (2025, in prep.).

Variable	th_{sup}^{mort}	th_{inf}^{mort}	th_{sup}^{opt}	th_{inf}^{opt}
SST (°C)	33	6	25	17
WH (m)	2.5	0	0.10	0.01
VM (m s ⁻¹)	0.92 ^a	0.05	0.80 ^b	0.65 ^b
CO ₂ (mg L ⁻¹)	12	0.5	0.60 ^b	0.57 ^b
SO (psu)	44	5	38	15
pH	9	5.5	8.5	7
O ₂ (mg L ⁻¹)	10	2.7	9	7

From a modelling perspective, Table 1 formalises the tolerance window for each environmental driver, ensuring comparability among variables before aggregation. Each trapezoidal function is continuous and monotonic, allowing their algebraic integration through non-linear operators such as the Einstein sum and product. From an ecological standpoint, the shape of each membership function reflects the physiological constraints imposed by temperature, hydrodynamics, salinity, and dissolved gases, thus translating complex biophysical limits into quantitative suitability gradients.

2.3. Einstein aggregation operators

To combine individual SIs into MSIs, we applied Einstein's sum and product operators [43], which allow a tunable balance between compensatory and limiting effects:

$$A \oplus_E B = \frac{A + B}{1 + AB}, \quad (3)$$

$$A \otimes_E B = \frac{AB}{2 - (A + B - AB)}. \quad (4)$$

The product operator propagates low values (emphasising limiting factors), while the sum allows compensation between variables. Importantly, both operators preserve the [0, 1] interval of the original suitability indices, ensuring that aggregated values remain interpretable as degrees of suitability.

The choice of Einstein operators over alternative fuzzy aggregation methods—such as standard t-norms (e.g., algebraic product, Łukasiewicz t-norm), t-conorms (e.g., probabilistic sum), or other parametric families like Hamacher, Frank, or Yager operators [?]—is motivated by their particularly favourable mathematical and ecological properties for aquaculture suitability modelling:

1. **Smooth non-linearity:** Einstein operators provide smooth, differentiable transitions across the entire suitability range. Unlike the strict minimum (Gödel t-norm) or maximum operators, which create discontinuities at threshold boundaries, Einstein operators generate gradual response surfaces that better mirror the continuous physiological responses of marine organisms to environmental gradients [?].

2. **Balanced sensitivity:** The Einstein product exhibits intermediate behaviour between the algebraic product ($A \cdot B$) and the minimum operator. This means it is sensitive to limiting factors without being as extreme as the ‘weakest link’ minimum, which ignores all information from non-limiting variables. Conversely, the Einstein sum is less compensatory than the probabilistic sum ($A + B - AB$), preventing excessive buffering when multiple stressors co-occur [43].
3. **Biological plausibility:** Marine species such as *S. aurata* exhibit tolerance windows wherein organisms can survive suboptimal conditions in one variable if other conditions are favourable (compensatory mechanism), but cannot survive if any single variable reaches a lethal threshold (limiting mechanism). Einstein operators naturally capture this duality: the sum models compensatory interactions between moderate stressors, while the product propagates the effect of critical limiting factors. Standard arithmetic means would over-compensate (masking lethal events), while strict minimums would ignore the buffering capacity that allows survival under moderate multi-stressor scenarios.
4. **Transparency and reproducibility:** Unlike weighted linear combinations, which require subjective weight assignment, Einstein operators derive aggregated suitability directly from the component indices without additional parameters. This enhances transparency, facilitates stakeholder communication, and ensures reproducibility across studies.

To illustrate the behaviour of these operators, Figure 1 shows the combined suitability of two generic variables (ranging from 0 to 1) under Einstein’s product (left) and sum (right).

Figure 1. Two-dimensional heatmaps of composite suitability values for two generic variables under Einstein’s product (left) and sum (right) operators.

To move beyond single SI assessments, we constructed MSIs by aggregating individual fuzzy coefficients. In this framework, we considered not only the contemporaneous suitability of each environmental variable, but also its potential delayed effects on mortality. Suitability scores were therefore extracted at multiple time lags (0, 1, 3, and 6 days), recognising that adverse conditions may influence fish health with a delay.

2.4. Validation and sensitivity analysis

Building on these contemporaneous and lagged suitability scores, we generated 3000 MSIs by randomly selecting subsets of variables and combining them through stochastic sequences of Einstein sum and product operators. This strategy produced a diverse ensemble of non-linear aggregation structures, ranging from compensatory to strongly lim-

iting behaviours, and allowed the data—rather than *a priori* assumptions—to reveal which combinations provided the most informative representation of environmental suitability.

Observed mortality percentages were then matched to the corresponding MSI values by time and location. For each mortality record, all 3000 candidate MSIs were computed, enabling correlation analysis between environmental suitability and mortality outcomes. Pearson correlation was used as the primary metric, as it consistently outperformed Spearman and Kendall alternatives in capturing the strength of association. Since higher MSI values indicate more suitable conditions (close to 1) whereas higher mortality reflects worse outcomes, correlations were calculated with $1 - \text{MSI}$ to ensure a consistent direction of association.

To ensure the robustness of the constructed indices, extensive simulations were conducted, and the Mean Squared Error (MSE) was calculated for model fitting. Although specific MSE values are omitted here for brevity, they were used to confirm the stability of the selected MSIs.

Moreover, to reduce noise from low mortality observations, the analysis was performed twice: (i) using the full dataset, and (ii) restricting to cases with mortality $> 2\%$, following evidence that very low mortality can mask environmental signals. From the 3000 indices evaluated, the 500 showing the strongest correlations with mortality were retained.

Variable frequency within these top indices, under both Einstein sum and product operators, was then analysed to identify the most influential predictors, while co-occurrence matrices quantified how often variable pairs appeared together, providing insight into potential joint effects. This procedure constitutes a **structural sensitivity analysis**, assessing how robust the observed mortality–suitability associations are to changes in index formulation.

To visualise these relationships, heatmaps were used to represent the correlations between mortality and the 500 MSIs with the strongest associations.

After identifying the MSI that was both informative and interpretable—showing a strong association with mortality while retaining a meaningful set of contributing variables—we compared the Einstein-based framework with classical multivariate approaches to assess its relative performance.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was used to explore the structure of the environmental suitability dataset and identify groups of highly correlated variables. PCA was applied to centred and scaled suitability time series (lagged and non-lagged), with missing values removed.

Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR) was then used as a supervised approach to relate environmental suitability variables (predictors) to observed mortality (response). This method extracts latent components that maximise the covariance between predictors and response, and is particularly suited to collinear environmental datasets.

2.5. Spatio-temporal evaluation of optimal MSI

Long-term changes in environmental suitability were evaluated using the non-parametric Mann–Kendall (MK) test [36,37] applied to the selected MSI time series at each spatial grid cell. The MK statistic (τ) measures the strength and direction of monotonic trends. It is particularly suitable for ecological and oceanographic datasets due to noise and irregular sampling are common. Positive τ values indicate increasing suitability through time, whereas negative τ values denote declining suitability conditions.

All analyses and visualisations were implemented in R (v4.4.2) using the `ggplot2`, `patchwork`, `scales`, `FactoMineR`, `factoextra`, and `pls` libraries for multivariate analysis and plotting. Environmental datasets in `netCDF` format were processed with `ncdf4` and

`ncdf4helpers`, while spatial data manipulation used `sf`. Additional statistical computations were performed with `Kendall` and `energy`.

3. Results

This section presents the outcomes of the suitability analysis, focusing on: (i) identifying the MSIs most strongly associated with mortality events, (ii) evaluating spatio-temporal patterns of environmental suitability along the southeastern Spanish Mediterranean coast, and (iii) benchmarking the proposed approach against conventional multivariate methods, namely Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR).

3.1. Correlation patterns between composite Einstein indices and mortality

To explore the relationship between mortality and environmental suitability, Pearson correlations were calculated between observed mortality percentages and $1 - \text{MSI}$ values derived from 5000 randomly generated Einstein indices. Each MSI was constructed by combining individual suitability coefficients and their lagged versions (lags of 1, 3, and 6 days). Pearson's correlation was chosen because, after comparing with alternative measures of association (Spearman's rank correlation and Kendall's τ), it consistently yielded the strongest and most interpretable relationships with the mortality data.

Figures 2 and 3 summarise the association between mortality (%) and the set of MSIs built with Einstein operators. Each row corresponds to a MSI (identified by its ID on the y-axis), while each column represents an individual SI (possibly lagged) that can enter a MSI. Columns are ordered to first display indices combined via the Einstein *sum* (\oplus_E) and then via the Einstein *product* (\otimes_E). Cell colour encodes the correlation coefficient r between mortality percentage and the MSI of that row; only the top 500 composites with the largest r are shown.

A first comparison between panels reveals qualitatively similar column-wise patterns across the full data set (Fig. 2) and the subset restricted to observations with mortality $> 2\%$ (Fig. 3). In both cases, darker vertical bands reappear at the same columns, indicating that certain single SI participate repeatedly in the best-performing composites and tend to yield higher correlations whenever they are included. Quantitatively, restricting the analysis to mortality $> 2\%$ appreciably increases the magnitude of the correlations (colour scale extends to ~ 0.60 in Fig. 3 versus ~ 0.35 in Fig. 2). This suggests that low-mortality observations contribute measurement noise or unrelated variability that dilutes the signal; once these are excluded, relationships between environmental suitability and mortality emerge more clearly.

It is important to contextualize these correlation values. In field-based ecological research, correlation coefficients exceeding 0.4 are widely regarded as significant findings, given the inherent complexity and noise of natural systems. Values exceeding 0.8 are rarely observed in 'real world' environmental data; thus, the correlations of $r \approx 0.60$ achieved here represent a strong ecological signal.

The operator-wise ordering on the x-axis facilitates comparison between aggregation regimes. In the \oplus_E block (left half), coloured tiles are more continuous and widespread, consistent with the compensatory nature of the Einstein sum: several moderately unfavourable factors can jointly raise risk. In the \otimes_E block (right half), colour concentrates in narrower, more intense streaks, reflecting the "weakest-link" behaviour of the Einstein product.

Across both operators, the most prominent contributors are the indices related to *wave height* (WH) and to the *velocity modulus* (VM). In particular, the column corresponding to WH with a six-day lag (WH, lag 6) stands out as a persistent vertical band among the top composites, and VM (at several lags) shows a similar, albeit slightly less pronounced, pattern. By contrast, other variables such as sea-surface temperature (SST), pH, oxygen

(O₂) or salinity (SO) yield more diffuse or context-dependent signals. The dominance of lags in the 3–6 day range points to delayed effects, in line with the notion that energetic wave events and local hydrodynamics precede mortality peaks by several days.

Figure 2. Heatmap of correlations between mortality percentage and Einstein composite indices using all available mortality data. Indices are sorted by correlation strength, with darker tones indicating stronger correlations.

Figure 3. Heatmap of correlations where mortality percentage exceeds 2%. Stronger and more consistent associations emerge once low-mortality records are excluded, reducing noise and measurement uncertainty.

3.2. Contribution of individual variables

Table 2 summarises the frequency with which each single SI appears among the 500 Einstein indices most strongly correlated with mortality.

Table 2. Frequency of each variable among the 500 Einstein indices most strongly correlated with mortality, across different time lags (0, 1, 3, 6 days). Results are shown separately for indices built with the Einstein product (\otimes_E) and the Einstein sum (\oplus_E).

Variable	lag 0	lag 1	lag 3	lag 6
\otimes_E WH	0.16	0.18	0.19	0.68
\otimes_E CO ₂	0.18	0.18	0.21	0.18
\otimes_E VM	0.24	0.22	0.23	0.21
\otimes_E O ₂	0.23	0.24	0.23	0.22
\otimes_E PH	0.24	0.24	0.23	0.18
\otimes_E SO	0.23	0.24	0.21	0.21
\otimes_E SST	0.19	0.20	0.20	0.20
\oplus_E WH	0.27	0.28	0.25	0.32
\oplus_E CO ₂	0.27	0.28	0.27	0.30
\oplus_E VM	0.28	0.24	0.26	0.28

A key finding is the dominant role of *wave height at lag 6*, which appears in 68% of the product-based indices. This suggests that adverse wave conditions six days prior to mortality events exert a critical and delayed influence on fish survival. Other variables (e.g., velocity modulus, oxygen, pH, salinity) appear with moderate and relatively uniform frequencies (20–24%).

3.3. Variable co-occurrence patterns

Figure 4 (omitted for brevity, refer to Supplementary Materials) presents the co-occurrence matrix. A prominent feature is the vertical and horizontal banding associated with *wave height at lag 6*, which appears in a large fraction of the top-performing composites. This dominant behaviour is consistent with the “weakest-link” property of the Einstein product. In contrast, variables entering through the Einstein sum operator show more balanced co-occurrence patterns, suggesting compensatory effects.

Figure 4. Co-occurrence matrix of variable pairs across the 500 best-performing Einstein indices. Darker colours indicate higher co-occurrence frequencies.

3.4. Selection of the composite index

The selected MSI combined *wave height at lag 6* and *velocity modulus at lag 3* using the Einstein sum operator. This formulation reinforces the leading role of wave conditions while highlighting the contribution of prior current dynamics. For this reason, we prioritised simplicity and selected the MSI defined solely by WH lag 6 \oplus_E VM lag 3. This index, despite ranking only 15th by correlation, captures the two variables most consistently associated with mortality, achieves a correlation comparable to the more complex alternatives ($r \approx 0.60$), and remains easily interpretable.

Figure 5 shows the two-dimensional MSI response. The plot highlights how unsuitable conditions arise when either variable falls outside its tolerance window. High wave heights (> 2 m) and very low or high current velocities (< 0.05 m/s or > 0.9 m/s) yield composite values close to zero (red areas).

Figure 5. Composite suitability surface obtained by combining wave height (WH) and current velocity modulus (VM) through Einstein’s sum operator.

Figure 6 displays the spatial distribution of the 5th percentile (Q5), mean, and 95th percentile (Q95) values of the selected MSI. The mean index values indicate generally favorable conditions (0.65–0.80) throughout most of the domain. However, the Q5 distribution highlights zones—particularly in northern and offshore areas—where suitability occasionally drops below 0.4.

3.5. Spatio-temporal trends in suitability

To assess long-term changes, the Mann–Kendall test was applied to the selected MSI. Figure 7 shows the spatial distribution of Kendall’s τ . Positive values (blue tones) indicate gradual increases in suitability, particularly in offshore areas to the east of Alicante, where improvements extend up to 40–50 km from the coast. Negative values (red tones), by contrast, are concentrated closer to the coast, reflecting a systematic decline in suitability in nearshore zones.

3.6. Benchmarking against PCA and PLSR

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied but yielded very poor explanatory performance. None of the first five components showed a meaningful correlation with mortality (highest correlation $r = -0.24$). Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR) performed better; Component 10 showed the strongest correlation with mortality percentage (Pearson $r = 0.53$), outperforming other components. This component was dominated by lagged

Figure 6. Summary location values of einstein coefficient.

Figure 7. Spatial distribution of Kendall's τ coefficient for the composite Einstein index. Blue tones indicate positive monotonic trends (increasing suitability), while red tones denote negative trends (declining suitability).

wave height and oxygen contributions. However, the direct interpretability of PLSR scores is limited compared to the transparent Einstein formulation, and its predictive power did not exceed that of the simpler Einstein MSI ($r \approx 0.60$).

4. Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate the utility of coupling fuzzy membership functions with Einstein aggregation operators to model environmental suitability for marine aquaculture. By moving beyond rigid binary thresholds and linear combinations, this framework captures the complexity of biological responses to multiple stressors while maintaining operational transparency for decision-makers.

4.1. Hydrodynamic Stress as a Key Mortality Driver

The structural sensitivity analysis revealed a striking dominance of hydrodynamic variables, specifically wave height (WH) and current velocity (VM), over biogeochemical

variables in driving mortality events for *Sparus aurata* in the study region. Crucially, the strongest association was found with wave height at a lag of 6 days. This delayed response is biologically consistent with the etiology of stress-induced mortality in aquaculture. Intense wave action causes immediate mechanical stress, abrasion against cage nets, and disruption of feeding behavior [16]. However, mortality is often not instantaneous; rather, the physical damage to the skin and mucus layer serves as a gateway for secondary bacterial infections, while sustained cortisol elevation leads to immunosuppression that manifests as mortality days after the storm event has passed [2]. The detection of this specific lag validates the importance of including temporal dynamics in suitability modelling, a feature often overlooked in static HSI approaches.

4.2. Methodological Performance: Einstein vs. Conventional Methods

The comparison between the proposed Einstein-based MSI and standard multivariate techniques highlights the advantages of the former in ecological risk assessment contexts where both predictive power and interpretability are valued. PCA failed to identify mortality drivers, likely because the variance in environmental data is not necessarily aligned with biological risk gradients (e.g., a rare lethal wave event contributes little to total variance but drives all mortality). PLSR performed moderately well ($r = 0.53$) but required 10 latent components to approach the predictive power that the Einstein MSI achieved with just two variables ($r \approx 0.60$). Furthermore, the Einstein sum operator provided a transparent mechanism to represent the compensatory nature of the environment—where favorable currents can mitigate moderate wave stress—without obscuring the limiting nature of extreme events. This transparency is vital for stakeholders who need to understand *why* a site is classified as suitable or unsuitable, something often lost in the "black box" of latent variable methods.

4.3. Implications for Spatial Planning and Climate Adaptation

The spatio-temporal trend analysis offers critical insights for the future of aquaculture in the region. The Mann-Kendall tests revealed a divergent pattern: nearshore areas are experiencing a significant decline in suitability, likely driven by increasing coastal energetic events or temperature anomalies not fully captured by the mortality correlation but present in the long-term trend. Conversely, offshore areas east of Alicante show a positive trend in suitability. This finding aligns with the broader push towards offshore aquaculture [?], suggesting that moving operations into deeper waters is not only a strategy to avoid coastal conflict but also an adaptation to climate change, capitalizing on more stable and improving environmental conditions.

4.4. The Role of Temperature and Data Limitations

Interestingly, Sea Surface Temperature (SST) did not emerge as a primary predictor of acute mortality in the correlation analysis, despite the well-documented thermal sensitivity of *S. aurata*. This may be due to the nature of the dataset: if farms are already sited within generally thermal-safe zones, mortality may be driven by stochastic storms rather than thermal trends. However, this does not negate the long-term threat of warming. As noted in the results, satellite data limitations (e.g., surface vs. water column stratification) might mask sub-surface thermal stress. Future iterations of this model should incorporate in-situ logger data to better resolve the vertical thermal structure.

5. Conclusions

This study developed and evaluated a multivariate suitability index (MSI) framework for marine aquaculture in the southeastern Spanish Mediterranean, integrating fuzzy membership functions, non-linear Einstein operators, lagged environmental responses,

and empirical validation against mortality data of *Sparus aurata*. The results highlight several key insights that advance both the methodological repertoire and the ecological understanding of environmental constraints on aquaculture sustainability.

First, the use of trapezoidal membership functions proved effective in translating species-specific physiological thresholds into continuous suitability indices (SI). Unlike crisp cut-offs, fuzzy functions allowed a gradual and ecologically realistic representation of tolerance windows, capturing both optimal and lethal conditions. This approach maintains transparency and biological relevance, ensuring that suitability estimates capture the full continuum of sublethal stress experienced by farmed fish.

Second, the adoption of Einstein sum and product operators for aggregating individual SIs introduced a novel, non-linear mechanism to model stressor interactions. The product operator propagated the influence of the most limiting variable, reflecting a 'weakest link' dynamic that aligns with ecological realities such as hypoxia or extreme wave exposure triggering mortality regardless of other conditions. Conversely, the sum operator demonstrated a compensatory behaviour, whereby sustained favourable conditions in certain variables could buffer the negative effects of others. This duality provided a flexible means of quantifying both additive resilience and limiting constraints within the same framework.

Third, the systematic exploration of thousands of MSIs revealed consistent ecological patterns. Among all environmental drivers, wave height with a six-day lag emerged as the most critical predictor of mortality, underscoring the delayed but severe impact of hydrodynamic stress on fish health. This finding emphasizes the need to consider not only instantaneous conditions but also cumulative or lagged environmental exposures when assessing site suitability. Ocean current velocity with a three-day lag also contributed significantly, suggesting that sub-acute hydrodynamic forcing modulates environmental conditions relevant to fish survival.

Fourth, the Mann–Kendall trend analysis uncovered spatially coherent patterns of change in environmental suitability. Positive trends in offshore waters to the east areas of Alicante point to gradually improving conditions, whereas nearshore waters showed consistent declines. Although the magnitude of Kendall's τ was modest, within the bounded 0–1 suitability scale such values denote persistent and ecologically meaningful shifts. This spatial differentiation highlights the dynamic nature of aquaculture environments under climate change, distinguishing emerging refugia from zones of increasing risk.

From a methodological standpoint, this study demonstrates the added value of combining fuzzy membership functions with non-linear algebraic aggregation and empirical validation. The integration of lagged variables and trend detection further advances the state of the art, aligning suitability indices more closely with ecological processes and management needs. The empirical link to observed mortality is particularly critical, moving beyond theoretical indices towards operational indicators that can directly inform aquaculture management.

In sum, the proposed MSI offers a robust and ecologically grounded tool for assessing aquaculture site suitability under changing environmental conditions. Future work should extend the framework by incorporating additional biogeochemical stressors (e.g., nutrients, carbonate chemistry) and validating results against multi-year farm performance data. However, the reliability of such analyses ultimately depends on the quality of the underlying observations. The mortality records available for this study are notoriously sparse and noisy, limiting the strength of ecological inference. Highlighting this limitation is essential: without investment in systematic, high-quality monitoring, even the most advanced methodological frameworks cannot deliver their full potential in guiding evidence-based decision-making for sustainable aquaculture in the Mediterranean and beyond.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript: Pending

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